

THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS

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Today, it is aimed at ensuring the safety of the development of the economy of our country, supporting them through direct and open communication with business entities and small business owners, and replacing exports and imports. special economic zones play an important role in attracting foreign direct investments to support the rapid development of goods production and logistics.

Launching of new production facilities based on modern technologies in our country, more active and large-scale involvement of regions in mastering the production of competitive and export-oriented industrial products, production, engineering, communication, road transport, free economic zones can be given as a clear example as the most optimal factor for improving and expanding the attraction of foreign direct investments to ensure the rapid development of social infrastructure and logistics services. At the same time, the economies of developing countries, unlike developed countries, focus primarily on achieving a high level of industrialization, i.e.: radical modernization of industry, attracting foreign investment, improving the skills and abilities of employees and introduction of new modern technologies. Special economic zones are important in this regard.

A special economic zone is a special economic zone with the purpose of attracting foreign direct investment and local investment, high-quality technologies and advanced management experience for the rapid socio-economic development of a certain area, within the defined limits and is a territory with a special legal regime. Organization of special economic zones can be as follows:

- free economic zones;
- special scientific and technological zones;
- tourist and recreational zones;
- free trade zones;
- special industrial zones.

Free economic zone - establishment of new production facilities, development of high-tech production, active involvement in the development of production of modern competitive, import-substituting, export-oriented ready-

made industrial products, as well as production, engineering-communication, the territory established for the purpose of ensuring the development of road transport, social infrastructure and logistics services.

A special scientific and technological zone is an area where scientific organizations and other organizations in the field of scientific activity (technological parks, technology distribution (technology transfer) centers, innovation clusters, venture funds, business incubators, etc.) are gathered for the purpose of developing innovation infrastructure.

Tourist-recreational zone - it includes modern touristic infrastructure objects (hotel complexes, cultural-healthcare, trade-entertainment and other touristic objects), special activity and seasonal recreational recreation zones necessary for the purpose of providing services to tourists an area that will be established for the implementation of investment projects related to the establishment of conditions.

Free trade zones include consignment warehouses, areas with special customs and tax regimes, as well as areas for processing, packing, sorting, and storing goods.

A special industrial zone is an area where a special regime of management, economic and financial activity is introduced. Special industrial zones include service and production zones formed by allocating land plots for the establishment of necessary administrative, scientific-technological, production, engineering-communication, road transport and social infrastructure.

Special economic zones are established for a period of 30 years based on the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The borders, type of activity and duration of activity of this zone will be changed based on the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. We should know that the management board of special economic zones is chaired by the chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, where the zone is located, and the mayors of the regions and the city of Tashkent. By establishing the directorate of the special economic zone (a legal entity in the form of a state unitary enterprise established to ensure the operation and management of the special economic zone), a special legal regime is implemented in the zone.

The following areas are important for attracting foreign direct investments to Uzbekistan and developing the activities of Special Economic Zones:

- Further simplification of the tax mechanism (reduction of tax rates, reduction of the tax rate for some types of activities)

- Improving the financial and credit mechanism (providing state subsidies for MIZ residents, lowering loan interest rates for Special Economic Zones residents)
- Development and modernization of logistics system;
- Extending the period of privilege for residents of special economic zones;
- Providing assistance from the state in relations related to export.

Table 1. Distribution of special economic zones and small economic zones in our republic*

Areas	Special Economic Zones	Small economic zones	Total
The Republic of Karakalpakstan	2	12	14
Andijan	1	19	20
Bukhara	2	17	19
Jizzakh	2	22	24
Kashkadarya	-	24	24
Navoi	1	7	8
Namangan	2	44	46
Samarkand	1	35	36
Surkhandarya	2	26	28
Syrdarya	2	13	15
Tashkent	4	18	22
Ferghana	1	40	41
Ferghana	1	11	12
Tashkent city	-	8	8

**(recycled material by the author)*

As can be seen from the above-mentioned table 1, Namangan region is the clear leader and most experienced region in our country in terms of the establishment of special and small economic zones. Fergana region is next with a small margin. This shows that the regions of the Fergana Valley are the leaders and experts in terms of direct foreign investment in the economy of our country through the establishment of special economic zones. As a result of such changes and opportunities, the standard of living of the population in the regions of the Fergana Valley, the economic and entrepreneurial potential is higher than that of the rest of the regions. The People's Republic of China is one of the most suitable

countries as a foreign experience in the establishment and management of special economic zones. Special economic zones are an important factor in the modernization of all sectors of the economy and the achievement of high-tech competitive production. It is no secret that the economic growth observed in China during the last thirty years was in fact an "economic miracle". Looking at its development trend, China was considered a closed economy until 1976. But in 1978, as a result of the "Open Door" policy carried out by Deng Xiaoping and reforms for this purpose, China began to integrate into the world economy, and China's GDP achieved an average growth of 10% per year. From 1979 to 2014, China's GDP per capita increased almost 16 times, from 195 US dollars to 3,583 US dollars. By 2010, it became the second largest economy in the world, overtaking Japan in terms of GDP. 500 million during this period. more than 100,000 people were freed from poverty

As a result of the research, it became clear that since 1978, a lot of work has been carried out within the framework of the "Open Doors" policy in order to transition from the centrally planned economy, which has prevailed for many years, to a modern market economy. In this regard, the establishment of different forms of special economic zones in China is one of the important directions, and the main goals of the establishment of Special Economic Zones were as follows:

- maximum attraction of foreign capital, development of scientific capacity sectors of industry on the basis of high technologies;
- effective participation in the international division of labor, increase in export volume and foreign currency income;
- development of the socio-economic situation in the areas where special economic zones are located, as in Hong Kong, Singapore and other newly industrialized countries;
- proper use of cheap and surplus labor force and rich raw material potential;
- acquiring management skills and training national personnel.

The vast experience of the People's Republic of China in establishing Special Economic Zones can serve as a sufficient example for Uzbekistan. The current investment policy in our country and the updates made to it make a great contribution to attracting foreign direct investments to free economic zones and to the economy of our country as a whole.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order for the national economy to reach a new state of quality, it is necessary to introduce new criteria and goals in the

field of economic policy. It will be necessary not only to strengthen the achieved achievements, but also to implement measures that ensure a new quality of economic growth. One of such aspects, in our opinion, is the analysis of the investment potential of the regions of the country, the results achieved as a result of attracting foreign investments, including the import of modern techniques and technologies from abroad and their assimilation and management experience, creation of new jobs and innovation projects. is mastery.

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